

Eight Arms, One Goal: The Transformation of Small-Scale Octopus Fisheries

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Small-scale octopus fisheries are globally important for livelihoods, food security, and local economies, particularly in developing countries due to their accessibility and low gear requirements. Meanwhile, the global demand for octopus has surged, especially in developed countries, making it a multi-billion-dollar industry. Yet, limited information exists on these fisheries, trade dynamics and value chains. This study reviews 19 small-scale octopus fisheries worldwide, examining their characteristics, supply chains, and challenges to their long-term viability and sustainability. Despite many commonalities, these fisheries can look quite different: some target domestic markets, while others supply international trade, mainly to the European Union and neighboring countries. Value addition along the chain is generally limited. Fishing methods are diverse (ranging from traps and handlines to gleaning and diving) with octopus contributing from less than 25% to over 75% of local landings, depending on the region. Management is also diverse, with some fisheries engaged in co-management or Fishery Improvement Projects (FIPs), and others transitioning from subsistence to commercial operations. Common challenges include weak monitoring and enforcement, illegal fishing, low economic returns, and inequities within value chains. However, promising opportunities exist: high international demand, digital tools for data collection and marketing, market diversification, value addition, and community organization. This analysis highlights the diversity and transformation of small-scale octopus fisheries, their integration into markets, and the need for inclusive strategies to ensure their long-term sustainability.

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